

A Benchtop Approach to Conducted Emissions Testing According to CISPR 25 Using the Voltage Method

Sebastian Westerhold¹

¹Independent Researcher, Baltic Lab, Kiel, Germany

E-mail: sebastian@baltic-lab.com

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7965-3140>

Abstract

This paper presents a structured and repeatable benchtop methodology for performing conducted electromagnetic emission measurements in accordance with CISPR 25 / DIN EN IEC 55025 using the voltage method. The work details the implementation of a largely standard-compliant test setup, including reference ground plane, line impedance stabilization network configuration, power-supply conditioning, cabling, and device-under-test support, with particular emphasis on measurement repeatability and practical constraints encountered outside accredited test facilities. Pre-compliance measurements are carried out using a modern spectrum analyzer controlled by dedicated EMC measurement software, with appropriate application of correction factors, detector settings, and bandwidths as required by the standard. In addition, a non-standard extension for separating differential-mode and common-mode noise components is demonstrated as an effective diagnostic aid for emission source localization and filter development. While the proposed benchtop approach does not replace accredited compliance testing in shielded environments, the results show that it provides reliable and meaningful pre-compliance data, enabling early detection of conducted-emission issues, informed design iteration, and increased confidence prior to formal certification testing.

Keywords: CISPR 25, Conducted Emissions, Automotive EMC, Pre-Compliance

1. Introduction

Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) is a critical aspect of electronic system design, particularly in automotive and transportation-related applications, where unintended electromagnetic emissions can impair the operation of sensitive radio and communication systems. Despite its importance, practical access to EMC measurement techniques remains limited outside accredited laboratories, largely due to the cost and complexity of test equipment and the perceived opacity of applicable standards. As a result, early-stage design validation and exploratory measurements are often deferred until late in the development cycle, increasing both technical risk and development cost.

This paper addresses this gap by presenting a benchtop methodology for conducted-emissions measurements that is closely aligned with the requirements of CISPR 25 (and DIN

EN IEC 55025), while remaining practical and cost-effective (Fig. 1). The proposed setup is intentionally designed to be largely standard-compliant, with all deviations from the formal requirements explicitly identified and technically justified. This approach enables meaningful pre-compliance measurements while maintaining traceability to the standardized test methods used in accredited compliance laboratories.

CISPR 25 applies to electrical and electronic components intended for use in vehicles, boats, and other systems powered by internal combustion engines. The standard specifies limits and measurement procedures intended to protect on-board radio receivers from conducted and radiated radio-frequency disturbances in the frequency range from 150 kHz to 108 MHz [1]. Although the standard addresses both conducted and radiated emissions, this work focuses exclusively on conducted emissions.

For conducted-emissions testing, CISPR 25 defines two alternative measurement approaches: the voltage method and the current method. The work presented here is based on the voltage method, which is the most space-efficient configuration and therefore well suited to benchtop implementation. Importantly, the voltage method is also the primary approach used in accredited compliance testing and forms the basis for related measurements using RF current probes as well as for radiated-emissions testing according to the same standard. These measurement variants differ mainly in secondary aspects, such as minimum reference ground-plane dimensions and specific setup details, while sharing a common underlying measurement philosophy.

Figure 1: Overview of the benchtop CISPR 25 conducted emissions (voltage method) test setup

2. Method

2.1 Reference Ground Plane and Grounding

For conducted-emissions measurements using the voltage method, the reference ground plane is required to have minimum dimensions of 100 cm × 40 cm and to be fabricated from copper, brass, bronze, or galvanized steel, with a minimum thickness of 0.5 mm [1]. In the setup described here, a galvanized steel sheet with dimensions of 100 cm × 40 cm and a thickness of 2 mm is employed (Fig. 2). To mitigate the risk posed by sharp edges and corners, two 1 m lengths of rubber edge protection are installed along the perimeter of the plate.

Figure 2: 100 cm × 40 cm galvanized steel sheet, 2 mm thick, used as the reference ground plane

The reference ground plane is required to be positioned at a height of 90 cm ± 10 cm above the floor. In the setup described, a bench height of 85 cm is used, which lies within the range specified by the standard.

According to CISPR 25, measurements are to be conducted in an anechoic chamber or a shielded room [1]. This requirement is incompatible with a genuinely benchtop-oriented pre-compliance setup and is therefore not implemented in the configuration presented. Although the omission of a fully shielded environment significantly simplifies the setup, it increases susceptibility to background noise and external electromagnetic interference, which may affect measurement accuracy. Consequently, a background scan should be performed prior to testing to verify that ambient interference remains at least 6 dB below the applicable limit.

Figure 3: Reference ground plane bonded to earth ground

Under fully compliant conditions, the reference ground plane would be bonded to the shielded enclosure using multiple grounding straps spaced no more than 30 cm apart, with each strap exhibiting a length-to-width ratio not exceeding 7:1 [1]. Owing to the absence of a suitable shielded enclosure, this requirement cannot be fully realized. Instead, the reference ground plane is connected to earth using a single grounding conductor with a cross-sectional area of 6 mm² (Fig. 3). While this simplified grounding arrangement is generally adequate for pre-compliance measurements, it may slightly reduce repeatability and introduce minor measurement deviations when compared to a fully standard-compliant installation.

2.2 Line Impedance Stabilization Network (LISN)

A line impedance stabilization network (LISN), designated as an artificial network (AN) in CISPR standards, constitutes a key element of conducted emissions measurements. Its primary function is to establish a defined and reproducible impedance between the power supply and the device under test (DUT), while simultaneously isolating the DUT from external disturbances present on the supply

lines. This controlled boundary condition enables repeatable and accurate characterization of radio-frequency emissions generated by the DUT. In addition, the LISN couples the DUT-generated disturbance voltage to a standardized 50 Ω RF measurement port, allowing direct connection to a spectrum analyzer or measurement receiver.

Figure 4: Two TekBox TBL0510-1 5 μH LISNs securely bonded to the reference ground plane using copper tape strips; the factory-installed 1 μF capacitor on the ground-return LISN (right) has not yet been removed

For conducted emissions measurements in accordance with CISPR 25, the LISN shall exhibit a nominal inductance of 5 μH, conform to the impedance characteristic specified in the norm, and be mounted directly on the reference ground plane with its enclosure electrically bonded to the plane. In the setup described here, two TekBox TBL0510-1 LISNs are employed (Fig. 4). These LISNs comply with the normative requirements regarding impedance magnitude (Fig. 5), impedance phase angle, and isolation [4].

Figure 5: Measured impedance of the TBL0510-1 5 μH LISN, 100 kHz – 110 MHz, source terminals shorted [3]

The number of LISNs required depends on the device under test (DUT) and the length of its supply cables. For a DUT with a single positive supply and ground, and a supply cable of 20 cm or less, a single LISN is sufficient (Fig. 6). In this configuration, referred to in the standard as a "locally grounded" DUT, the ground return of the DUT is directly connected to the reference ground plane.

Figure 6: Conducted emission measurement, voltage method, DUT with power return line locally grounded [3]

A more commonly employed configuration is the "remotely grounded" variant, in which both the positive supply line and the ground return are routed through separate LISNs (Fig. 7). This dual-LISN arrangement can also facilitate the separation of differential- and common-mode noise, which is advantageous for troubleshooting.

Figure 7: Conducted emission measurement, voltage method, DUT with power return line remotely grounded [3]

A 1 μF capacitor is required in parallel at the LISN's source terminal on the positive supply line (Fig. 7). In the TBL0510-1 units employed, this capacitor comes pre-installed by the manufacturer (Fig. 4).

Additionally, a 1000 μF capacitor is installed between the positive input terminals of both LISNs (Fig. 8). According to the standard, this capacitor is required only for components that are part of the ignition system; otherwise, it may be omitted. In this configuration, a Würth Elektronik WCAP-ATG8 capacitor rated for up to 63 V is utilized [12].

Figure 8: LISNs with a factory-installed 1 μF capacitor on the positive supply line LISN (left) and an externally installed 1000 μF capacitor between the two LISNs

2.3 DUT Placement, Supply Line Routing and Support

The device under test (DUT) is positioned on a support composed of non-conductive material with a relative permittivity of $\epsilon_r \leq 1.4$, at a height of $50 \text{ mm} \pm 5 \text{ mm}$ above the reference ground plane. Supply lines are routed in a straight path on a similar low-permittivity support at the same height (Fig. 9). All sides of the DUT maintain a minimum distance of 100 mm from the edges of the reference ground plane. The power supply ground return is connected to the reference ground plane between the supply and the LISN.

Figure 9: Supply lines and DUT mounted on a low-permittivity support

In this setup, a 50 mm-thick polyethylene (PE) protective foam is employed. Although bulk PE exhibits a relative permittivity of approximately 2.25, exceeding the permissible $\epsilon_r \leq 1.4$, the high air content of the foam reduces its effective ϵ_r to roughly 1.6, slightly above the limit. A more suitable alternative is expanded polystyrene (styrofoam), which typically exhibits a relative permittivity only marginally above 1.

2.4 Load Simulator

If the DUT is a stand-alone component requiring only power and no additional external connections, the inclusion of a load is unnecessary. Otherwise, a load must be incorporated into the test setup, and all actuator and sensor connections that normally interface with the DUT should be present during measurement. For simple loads, a fixed resistor may be sufficient, whereas more versatile implementations employ an active load. Although the term "load simulator" may appear excessive for basic configurations, it reflects the terminology specified in the standard.

Figure 10: Self-powered active load configured as load simulator and connected to the DUT

The load simulator integrates sensors and actuators and terminates the harness connected to the DUT [1]. It is preferably positioned directly on the reference ground plane. For simulators with a metal housing, the housing must be electrically bonded to the ground plane. Alternatively, the simulator may be placed in close proximity to the reference ground plane with proper electrical bonding, or outside the measurement chamber, provided the DUT's harness passes through an RF barrier and remains electrically bonded to the reference ground plane [2]. If the load simulator requires an independent power supply, its DC supply lines must be connected directly to the source and not routed through the LISNs.

Figure 11: TekBox TBOH02 self-powered active load used as a load simulator

In this setup, a TekBox TBOH02 self-powered active load is employed (Figs. 10 and 11). The load operates without an external supply, supports input voltages from 2 V to 70 V, can dissipate up to 10 A, and allows operation in both constant-current and constant-resistance modes. Accurate adjustment is achieved via a 10-turn potentiometer with dial, a range switch, and a precision reference, while the fully analog design minimizes the introduction of digital noise into supply-noise measurements [10].

2.5 Power Supply

The standard imposes stringent requirements on the power supply. During testing, the DC output voltage must be maintained within $\pm 10\%$ of its nominal value (Table 1), and any RF noise generated by the supply must remain at least 6 dB below the applicable limit [1].

Table 1: Test Voltages for Different Nominal Supply Levels [1]

Nominal Supply Voltage	Test Voltage
12 V	13 V \pm 1 V
24 V	26 V \pm 2 V
48 V	48 V \pm 4 V

Satisfying this requirement can be challenging even for well-regulated switch-mode power supplies. Although linear supplies are generally preferred, a switch-mode supply (PeakTech 6227, 0-60 V) was employed in combination with additional filtering to achieve the required 6 dB margin below the CISPR 25 Class 3 limits. Filtering between the power supply output and the LISN input was implemented using a Würth Elektronik WE-CLFS single-stage line filter [8] in conjunction with a WE-STAR-TEC snap-on ferrite [9]. The line filter was electrically bonded directly to the reference ground plane (Fig. 12).

Figure 12: Supply voltage input section showing the line filter (left) and connections to the LISNs

For more stringent emission limits, a 7 Ah sealed lead-acid battery was used as an alternative power source (Fig. 13). In this configuration, care must be taken to ensure that the supply voltage remains within the $\pm 10\%$ tolerance as the battery discharges during measurement. A practical interim solution is parallel operation of the battery with the power supply, where the battery's inherently low output impedance provides effective suppression of residual power-supply noise. To protect the LISNs in the event of an accidental short circuit, a fuse should be connected in series with the battery.

Figure 13: Sealed lead-acid battery with in-line fuse used as an alternative low-noise power supply source

2.6 Measurement Receiver & Software

The measuring instrument, including FFT-based receivers, shall comply with the requirements specified in CISPR 16-1-1 [1]. A detailed discussion of these requirements is beyond the scope of this work. Spectrum analyzers and scanning receivers are commonly employed for conducted-emissions measurements. The correct configuration and operation of spectrum analyzers for EMC pre-compliance testing is nontrivial and has been addressed extensively in the literature [5]. For practical implementation details using low-cost spectrum analyzers, dedicated

application notes are available and are referenced accordingly.

Table 2: CISPR Bandwidths [13]

Frequency Range	CISPR Filter Bandwidth
9 kHz – 150 kHz	200 Hz
150 kHz – 30 MHz	9 kHz
30 MHz – 1 GHz	120 kHz
> 1 GHz	1 MHz

For the test setup, a Rigol RSA5065N spectrum analyzer equipped with the EMI measurement option [6] was employed in conjunction with the TekBox EMCview PC software [7]. The EMI option provides the CISPR-compliant resolution bandwidths (Table 2) as well as standardized peak, quasi-peak, and average detectors required for conducted-emissions measurements.

Figure 14: EMCview software configured with CISPR 25 Class 3 limits and correction factors for the LISNs, transient limiter, and BNC-to-N RG223 cable

The EMCview software (Fig. 14) supports a wide range of spectrum analyzers, including entry-level instruments from Rigol and Siglent, and facilitates standard-compliant measurement workflows. After loading the relevant segment definitions, limit lines, and correction data, including LISN and cable corrections, measurements are executed in a largely automated manner. Resolution bandwidths and detector settings are applied automatically, and communication with the measurement instrument is established via USB or Ethernet.

3. Measurement

3.1 General Procedure

Conducted emissions on the supply lines are measured sequentially on the positive supply line and on the supply return line by connecting the spectrum analyzer to the measurement port of the corresponding LISN. Any additional

LISN inserted in the remaining supply line(s) shall have its measurement port terminated with a 50 Ω load [1].

Figure 15: Conducted emissions measurement of a DUT with CISPR 25 Class 3 limits; peak (purple) and average (green) spectra shown alongside average limit (red) and peak limit (blue)

Although CISPR 25 specifies limits for peak, quasi-peak, and average detectors (Tables 3 to 5), only the quasi-peak and average limits are legally binding for certification. Peak measurements are primarily used for rapid pre-compliance screening (Fig. 15) and diagnostic purposes, as compliance with peak limits alone does not ensure conformity. In accredited laboratories, peak detection is typically applied during initial scans or troubleshooting, whereas final compliance assessment is conducted exclusively using quasi-peak and average measurements in accordance with the standard.

Table 3: CISPR 25 Average Voltage Limits for CISPR 25 Classes 1 to 5 in dBμV [1]

Range (MHz)	Class 1	Class 2	Class 3	Class 4	Class 5
0.15 – 0.3	90	80	70	60	50
0.53 – 1.8	66	58	50	42	34
5.9 – 6.2	57	51	45	39	33
26 – 28	48	42	36	30	24
30 – 68	48	42	36	30	24
68 – 108	42	36	30	24	18

Table 4: CISPR 25 Voltage Peak Limits for CISPR 25 Classes 1 to 5 dBμV [1]

Range (MHz)	Class 1	Class 2	Class 3	Class 4	Class 5
0.15 – 0.3	110	100	90	80	70
0.53 – 1.8	86	78	70	62	54
5.9 – 6.2	77	71	65	59	53
26 – 28	68	62	56	50	44
30 – 41	68	62	56	50	44
41 – 88	58	52	46	40	34
88 – 108	62	56	50	44	38

Table 5: Voltage Quasi-Peak Limits for CISPR 25 Classes 1 to 5 in dB μ V [1]

Range (MHz)	Class 1	Class 2	Class 3	Class 4	Class 5
0.15 – 0.3	97	87	77	67	57
0.53 – 1.8	73	65	57	49	41
5.9 – 6.2	64	58	52	46	40
26 – 28	55	49	43	37	31
30 – 54	55	49	43	37	31
54 – 68	49	43	37	31	25
68 – 108	49	43	37	31	25

3.2 Background Scan

To ensure conformity with the standard, it is strongly recommended that measurements be preceded by a background scan conducted with the complete test setup in place while the device under test is disabled or removed. This procedure verifies that noise originating from external sources, including the power supply and ambient interference, remains at least 6 dB below the applicable limits (Fig. 16).

Figure 16: Background measurement evaluated against CISPR 25 Class 3 limits; peak (purple) and average (green) spectra shown alongside average limit (red) and peak limit (blue); grey traces below each limit indicate the required 6 dB margin

At a minimum, the background scan enables discrimination between emissions generated by the device under test and external interference, even when the background itself exceeds the specified limits. In non-shielded laboratory environments, external sources such as broadcast FM transmissions and lighting systems can couple into the measurement setup, particularly in the VHF range, and may independently exceed the limits (Fig. 17), representing a key limitation of benchtop measurements performed outside shielded facilities.

Figure 17: Background measurement with LED room lighting enabled, evaluated against CISPR 25 Class 3 limits; peak (purple) and average (green) spectra shown alongside average limit (red) and peak limit (blue) multiple limit exceedances observed above 30 MHz

3.3 Differential- and Common-Mode Separation

In cases where a device under test does not meet pre-compliance limits, effective troubleshooting requires identification of the dominant emission mechanism. Separation of differential- and common-mode noise is particularly valuable for locating the emission source and deriving appropriate mitigation measures (Fig. 18).

Although not explicitly specified in the standard, a dual-LISN configuration enables decomposition of the conducted noise components through linear signal combination.

In-phase summation of the noise voltages from both LISNs suppresses the differential-mode component and yields the common-mode component at twice the amplitude of a single-line measurement. Conversely, subtraction of the two signals, or summation with a 180° phase shift applied to one channel, suppresses the common-mode component and isolates the differential-mode component, likewise at twice the amplitude of a single-line measurement.

Such signal addition or subtraction may be implemented using the mathematical functions and FFT capabilities of a modern oscilloscope, with each LISN output connected to a separate input channel. While this approach is useful for rapid qualitative assessment, oscilloscope-based FFT measurements do not comply with the detector characteristics, sweep-time requirements, or bandwidth definitions specified by the standard, nor do they incorporate the frequency-dependent correction factors associated with the LISNs and test cables.

Figure 18: Conducted emissions measurement of a DUT with separated differential- and common-mode components, showing common-mode peak (CM PK), common-mode average (CM AVG), differential-mode peak (DM PK), and differential-mode average (DM AVG) spectra

For differential-mode and common-mode measurements intended for direct use in line-filter design, a properly characterized signal combiner used in conjunction with a measurement receiver or spectrum analyzer is required. In the presented setup, a TekBox TBLM2 LISN Mate is employed [11]. This device provides calibrated correction factors over the frequency range from 9 kHz to 110 MHz and operates as a dedicated separator for common-mode and differential-mode components. The LISN Mate is connected to the outputs of both LISNs, and the isolated differential-mode or common-mode signal is obtained from the corresponding output port (Fig. 19).

Figure 19: Modified test setup using a sealed lead-acid battery as a low-noise power source, with the LISN Mate installed for differential- and common-mode separation

4. Conclusion

This setup demonstrates that conducted-emissions measurements in accordance with CISPR 25 / DIN EN 55025 can be performed reliably on a standard laboratory bench using the voltage method. By implementing

disciplined grounding practices, controlled routing of supply lines, and a properly configured LISN-to-receiver measurement chain, repeatable and consistent data can be obtained. While this benchtop approach does not replace accredited compliance testing in an anechoic chamber or fully shielded environment, it provides a practical, low-cost methodology for early identification of emission issues, evaluation of design modifications, and preliminary EMC assessment prior to formal certification. The results suggest that such pre-compliance measurements can significantly improve design confidence and reduce the likelihood of failures in subsequent certified testing.

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